

Original article

Determination of vitamin D status of infants at the Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital, Azare: a pilot study

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Abstract

Background: The global variation in the prevalence of Vitamin D deficiency in infants informs WHO's recommendation for regional research to guide the formulation of region-specific guidelines for vitamin D supplementation. **Aim:** This cross-sectional pilot study was conducted in FUHSTHA, Bauchi state, to assess the feasibility of a proposed multicentre study on the status of vitamin D in infants. **Materials and Methods:** Following ethical approval, infants seen at the Paediatric department who fulfilled the inclusion criteria were consecutively recruited into the study until the sample size of 56 was attained. A structured questionnaire was applied to obtain relevant socio-demographic and clinical information. Any ambiguous question was noted, and the time taken for each participant encounter was documented. Blood samples taken from both mother and child were analysed in the laboratory for 25-hydroxycholecalciferol, serum calcium, albumin, alkaline phosphatase and other electrolytes. The average cost of laboratory investigations was computed. **Results:** Clinical and laboratory information from 53 infant-mother pairs was analysed. The mean serum Vitamin D levels were 27.3 (14.6) ng/ml for infants and 13.0 (10.9) ng/ml for mothers. Ten infants and 18 mothers had serum Vitamin D levels <10ng/l, giving the Vitamin D deficiency rates of 19.2% and 34.6% for infants and mothers, respectively. A 10 per cent consent decline rate was recorded, while about 45 minutes were required for a complete participant encounter. The cost of laboratory investigations was documented. **Conclusion:** The adopted methodology can achieve the objectives of the study. Modifications to the protocol for data collection will address observations on ease of data collection, while the computed cost of laboratory tests will improve the budget estimation process.

Keywords: Azare, Infants, Pilot study, Vitamin D

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Introduction

Vitamin D is essential for bone formation through its action on calcium and phosphorus metabolism. It also helps in the modulation of immune function. Its deficiency results in poor bone formation, which in its severe form presents as rickets, as well as increased susceptibility to infections, which is the underlying cause of recurrent infections in affected children.¹ Clinically, vitamin D-deficient young infants present with poor growth, frontal bossing, craniotabes and rachitic rosary. Bowed legs and swollen wrists are also encountered in severe vitamin D deficiency ¹.

Natural sources of vitamin D include Cod liver oil, egg yolk, beef liver and dairy products. The young infants depend on breast milk predominantly for their nutritional requirements. Vitamin D content of breast milk is, however, low, and exclusively breastfed babies receive less than 20% of the daily recommended dose of vitamin D from breast milk². Therefore, while exclusive breastfeeding is recommended for babies from birth to age six months to ensure optimisation of breast milk benefits, the natural deficiency in vitamin D makes it

imperative for infants to receive vitamin D supplementation.

Under the influence of UVB radiation, 7-dehydrocholesterol (7DHC) within the cells of the skin is photoisomerised to pre-vitamin D₃. After this initial photoisomerisation, the pre-vitamin D₃ undergoes a heat isomerisation in the skin to vitamin D₃, a process that takes several hours. The vitamin D₃ is first hydroxylated in the liver to 25-hydroxyvitamin D₃ (25(OH)D₃) and then again in the kidney to its active form, 1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D₃ (1,25(OH)₂D₃).³ Abundance of sunlight in most parts of Northern Nigeria does not, however, guarantee adequate vitamin D synthesis because some environmental, socio-cultural and behaviour-related factors may limit exposure to available sunlight.⁴

As a result of global variations in the prevalence and severity of vitamin D deficiency, the World Health Organization recommends regional research studies to support the development of region-specific guidelines on vitamin D supplementation in children.⁵

The prevalence of vitamin D deficiency is reportedly high in neonates, especially in preterm low birth weight babies and young infants in Nigeria. A prevalence rate of 41% was documented for children aged 0-24 months in Zaria⁶ and 12.6% among children with sickle cell anaemia in Lagos.⁷ Although vitamin D supplementation is essential for young infants, there is currently no guideline on this in Nigeria, notably due to the unavailability of sufficient data to drive the development of this all-important national document. This, therefore, calls for further fact-seeking clinical investigations.

A multicentre study was therefore designed to estimate the burden of vitamin D deficiency in infants in selected parts of the country, with the hope that a coordinated, synchronised study involving multiple centres would not only be more cost-effective but also have the potential to generate adequate data in a shorter time than individual single-centre studies. The specific objectives were to determine the prevalence of vitamin D deficiency in this category of children and document factors, including maternal vitamin D level, that may be associated with their vitamin D status. It is, however, imperative to assess the feasibility of such a large-scale multicentre study, especially with respect to the appropriateness of methodology and cost of laboratory investigations to forestall potential hindrances.

This pilot study was therefore conceived to assess the feasibility of the main study with specific attention to ease of data collection (obtaining consent for participation, information extraction from parents on cultural issues), availability of laboratory reagents for analysis, research personnel needed and cost of laboratory investigations. It was hoped that the data collected would not only **justify** the need for the full-scale study but would also provide evidence for protocol modification to ensure seamless research.

Aim and objectives

The pilot study was carried out to generate local evidence to justify the need for, and assess the feasibility of, the proposed large-scale multicentre study with the following specific objectives:

1. Determine the clarity of the data collection tool,
2. Document the proportion of mothers approached who declined to give consent for participation in the study.
3. Estimate the cost of laboratory investigations and data analysis.
4. Demonstrate alignment of results to the objectives of the main study as an indication of the appropriateness of the proposed research methodology.

Materials and Methods

Study site: Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital, Azare, A tertiary health institution with a full complement of Paediatric services (Emergency Paediatric Unit, Paediatric Medical Ward, Special Care Baby Unit, and General Paediatric Outpatient Unit), located in Katagum Local Government Area of Bauchi State. The 3 major seasons in Azare are the hot/dry season (March to May), Rainy season ((July to September) and the cold season (November to February). During these periods, extreme temperatures are often experienced with a peak of 101°F in May and nadir of 55°F in January. The people of Azare are predominantly Muslims (90%) while the primary economic activity is Farming.

Study type: Cross-sectional, pilot study

Subjects: Infants (0-12 months) attending the POPD or on admission in PMW or SCBU, who are on full enteral feeding and being cared for by their biological mothers. We excluded infants with clinical evidence of hepatic or renal disease, those who had recently been transfused (within 2 weeks of study), or had obvious congenital anomalies of the musculoskeletal system and those whose parents did not consent to participate in the study. **Sample size:** The formula for a cross-sectional study with qualitative outcome variable (proportion) was used to estimate the sample size required for the proposed multicentre study. $N = Z (1-\alpha/2)^2 \times P (1-P) \div d^2$.⁸ About 15% of the calculated sample size was decided a priori as the sample size for the pilot study.

$Z_{1-\alpha/2}$ = standard normal variate, which at 5% type 1 error is 1.96. (Level of significance $P < 0.05$)

p = prevalence of vitamin D deficiency from a previous study⁶ = 41%

d = Absolute error or precision (5%)

$\therefore n = 1.96 \times 1.96 \times 0.41 \times 0.59 \div (0.05 \times 0.05) = 372$.

Sample size for the pilot study was 15% of 372 = 55.8 ≈ 56.

Ethical approval for the pilot study was obtained from the Health Research Ethics Committee of the Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital before data collection commenced.

Subject recruitment and sample collection: Mothers of infants seen at the GOPD, PMW or SCBU who met the inclusion criteria were recruited consecutively (purposive sampling) into the study as soon as consent for participation was obtained. To obtain consent from the mothers, all information (documented) related to the research was read out and interpreted when necessary, and a signature or thumbprint was required as evidence of consent for participation. A structured questionnaire was then applied to obtain relevant maternal and child

socio-demographic information. Baby's gestational age, birth weight, drugs used in pregnancy, feeding pattern since delivery and details of multivitamin supplementation were noted and documented. Mothers were questioned about their regular mode of dressing with specific reference to the use or otherwise of the Hijab (the Islamic form of dressing that covers total body except the face). Where the response to the use of hijab was in the affirmative, the colour was documented. Every baby was examined, and any significant physical examination findings (jaundice, hepatomegaly, body swelling) were documented along with the weight, length and head circumference. The time taken for each participant encounter (consent, administration of questionnaire and blood collection) was noted. The ease with which participants responded to the questions and areas of ambiguity was also noted. We also noted the number of potential subjects who declined consent for participation in the study. Blood samples were then drawn from the baby and the mother into pre-labelled sample bottles specific for required investigations and taken to the laboratory for investigations.

Phlebotomy procedure: Under strict aseptic conditions, 2-3mls of free-flowing venous blood were withdrawn from every participating baby for laboratory estimation of serum 25-hydroxycholecalciferol (Vitamin D), calcium, phosphorus, alkaline phosphatase, urea, creatinine and serum albumin. Care was taken to avoid tourniquet application while drawing the specimen to avoid falsely elevated calcium levels. Maternal venous blood was also drawn at the same time to determine the maternal vitamin D level. Duplicates of the completed questionnaires were sent along with the samples to the laboratory as soon as the samples were collected. The sample bottles were checked at the point of delivery in the laboratory by both the personnel from the ward/clinic and the lab technician to ensure they were appropriately labelled, and the mother-infant paired samples were clearly sorted out.

Laboratory processing of blood samples: In the Laboratory, the specimens were allowed to clot and were thereafter centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes to separate the serum from the clotted red cells. Only non-haemolysed specimens were accepted for further processing. Following the separation of the components, the serum from each specimen was aliquoted into sterile cryovials labelled with the corresponding participant ID and stored at -20 °C until analysis.

Standard laboratory analytical protocols were followed. All samples were pooled and analysed on the same day, ensuring that the same batch of reagents was used across specimens while also avoiding repeat freezing and thawing cycles that would diminish the specimens' integrity. To begin, the stored specimens were removed from -20°C and allowed to warm to room temperature before analysis. Test reagents were reconstituted at room temperature for the various assays. Appropriate aliquots of the sera were then mixed with the reagents and introduced into the analyser. Alkaline phosphatase, inorganic phosphorus, calcium, creatinine, urea, and albumin were assayed using a CONTEC semi-auto biochemistry analyser (model: BC300, Contec Medical System Co., Ltd), while vitamin D concentration was

determined using a Finecare™ FIA Meter II Plus SE (Model No.: FS-114, Guangzhou Wondfo Biotech Co., Ltd). The results of the analysis were displayed on the monitor of the equipment and were documented and entered the excel sheet containing the socio-demographic information of the participants.

Data analysis: Data obtained from questionnaires were periodically reviewed for completion and transferred onto an Excel sheet. This was subsequently uploaded onto the SPSS platform (IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows version 26) for analysis. The mean (SD) and median values of Serum Vitamin D levels for infants and mothers were generated, and the values for infants were further disaggregated for sex and gestation. Based on definitions set for vitamin D deficient, insufficient and normal, a priori, the proportion of infants and mothers within each of the categories was computed and documented. The mean (SD) values for serum calcium, phosphorus, alkaline phosphatase, albumin and creatinine were also calculated. The results thus generated were summarised and tabulated. Results were however, not subjected to statistical tests of significance because this being a pilot study, was not adequately powered to meet the requirements for the validity of such statistical tests.

Results and Observations

1. Time taken to obtain consent, administer the questionnaire and take a blood sample for one mother-baby pair was about 45 minutes. The doctor involved also had to see other patients in the clinic or ward, and this led to prolonged waiting times for other patients who were not participating in the study. It also impacted the length of time required to recruit the total number of participants for the study.
2. About 10% of women whose children fulfilled the inclusion criteria and were thus provided the research consent information, declined consent for participation, and the excuse given by most of them was that they needed to contact their husbands for their consent.
3. The protocol included questions on maternal occupation, and responses obtained did not directly address the extent of exposure to the source of vitamin D (sunlight). The majority were housewives, and there was no follow-up question on how often they stayed outdoors for other activities.
4. The question on the use of Hijab was quite useful; however, very little additional information was obtained when mothers were asked about the colour of the hijab they wore. This was because quite a number of them used different colours of hijab on different occasions/days.

The total cost of sample bottles, needles, syringes, and consumables for blood collection, as well as reagents procured for laboratory analyses, was one million and thirty-three thousand Naira (N1,099,700) for 53 mother-

infant pairs (N20,750.00 per infant-mother pair). This is shown in Table 1

Table 1: Cost of sample bottles, needles/syringes, consumables (sample collection), and reagents for Laboratory analyses.

Item serial number	Item	Cost
1	Data entry (Excel sheet)	15,000
2	Data entry (SPSS)	50,000
3	Data analysis	50,000
4	Stationeries	30,000
5	Consumables for blood sample collection	31,700
6	Sample bottles	49,000
7	Reagents for laboratory tests	854,000
8	Laboratory scientist	20,000
9	Total cost (data collection and analysis)	1,099,700

General characteristics of the study population.

A total of 56 infants and their biological mothers were recruited into the study, out of whom 3 had incomplete data and were therefore excluded from the analysis. Thirty (56.7%) were males, and 9 (17.6%) were products of preterm gestation. While 98% had antenatal care, only 35 (67.3%) of the infants were delivered in a hospital, and the mean age of the mothers was 26.6(5.9) years. Most of the mothers (63.5%) were housewives, while only 6(11.5%) were gainfully employed, although about 65% had secondary and/or higher levels of education. The predominant religion among respondents was Islam, with 98% being Muslims. Although 98% of the infants were breastfed, 69.4% were fed breast milk substitutes (BMS) along with breast milk, while 2.0% were exclusively fed on BMS. Table 2 shows the general socio-demographic characteristics of study participants.

As depicted in Table 3 below, the mean serum Vitamin D levels were 27.3 (14.6) ng/ml for infants and 13.0 (10.9) ng/ml for mothers. The female infants had a slightly higher serum Vitamin D level [28.1 (15.3)] than the male infants [26.7 (14.4)], while the preterm infants had higher mean serum vitamin D levels [31.2 (18.4)] than the term infants [26.2 (13.9)]. Ten infants and 18 mothers had serum Vitamin D levels below 10ng/l, giving the Vitamin D deficiency rates of 18.9% and 34.0% for infants and their mothers, respectively. The corresponding prevalence rates of Vitamin D insufficiency were 13.5% and 57.7 % respectively.

Table 2: General Characteristics of infants and mothers

Characteristics	Frequency (%)
Sex (53)	
Male	30 (56.6%)
Female	23 (43.4%)
Gestation (51)	
Term	42 (82.4%)
Preterm	9 (17.6%)
Place of delivery (52)	
FUHSTHA	18 (34.6%)
Home	17 (32.7%)
Private Hospital	8 (15.4%)
Other public hospitals	6 (11.5%)
Maternity home	3 (5.8%)
ANC (51)	
Yes	50 (98.0%)
No	1 (2%)
Maternal Occupation (52)	
Housewife	33 (63.5%)
Civil servant	6 (11.5%)
Self employed	3 (5.8%)
Student	2 (3.8%)
Trading	8 (15.4)
Mean Maternal age-years (SD)	
	26.6 (5.9)
Religion (52)	
Islam	51 (98.1%)
Christianity	1 (1.9%)
Maternal Education (44)	
Primary	3 (5.7%)
Secondary	24 (42.3%)
Tertiary	12 (22.6%)
None	14 (26.4%)
Feeding type (49)	
Breast milk +water	14 (28.6%)56
Breast milk +Breast milk substitute	34 (69.4%)
Breast milk substitute alone	1 (2.0%)
Vitamin D supplement (53)	
Yes	6 (11.3%)
No	8 (15.1%)
Not known	39 (73.6%)

Table 3: Vitamin D levels/status of infants and mothers

Variable	Infant	Mother
Vitamin D level:		
Mean (SD)	27.3 (14.6)	13.0 (10.9)
Median (IQR)	24.0(14.6-8-9)	11.5 (8.6-15.7)
Male	26.7 (14.2)	
Female	28.1 (15.3)	
Preterm	31.2 (18.4)	
Term	26.2 (13.9)	
Vitamin D status		4 (7.7%)
Normal	35 (67.3%)	30 (57.7%)
Insufficient	7 (13.5%)	18 (34.0%)
Deficient	10 (18.9%)	

Definitions: Normal vitamin D level $\geq 20\text{ng/ml}$; 2. Insufficiency 11- $<20\text{g/ml}$; Deficient $\leq 10\text{ng/ml}$

Table 4 displays the serum vitamin D levels in infants and their association with factors that may influence these levels. The aim was to identify the direction of these relationships, if any, since the pilot study was not sufficiently powered for statistical analysis/tests to confirm the strength of any such relationships. Total body covering (Hijab+ Niqab), by mothers, use of BMS, prematurity, and female gender tended to be associated with a higher prevalence of vitamin D deficiency. The question on BMS use did not adequately address the duration and type of BMS taken by the infants.

Infants of mothers who were complete housewives or 'self-employed' also had a higher prevalence of vitamin D deficiency, while maternal level of education showed an inverse relationship with infant vitamin D status.

Table 4: Factors associated with serum vitamin D levels in infants

Tested variables	Vitamin D status		
	Normal (≥ 20 ng/ml)	Insufficient (10-<20ng/ml)	Deficient (<10ng/ml)
Mother's dressing mode			
Hijab	18 (72%)	4 (16%)	3 (12%)
Hijab + Niqab	18 (64.3%)	3 (10.7%)	7 (25%)
Infant feeding type			
BM + BMS	24 (70.6%)	4 (11.8%)	6 (17.6%)
Breast milk + water	8 (57.1%)	2 (14.3%)	4 (28.6%)
BMS	0 (0)	1 (100%)	0 (0)
Gender			
Male	19 (63.3%)	6(20.0%)	5 (16.7%)
Female	17 (73.9%)	1 (4.3%)	5 (21.7%)
ANC			
Yes	34 (68%)	7 (14%)	9(18%)
No	2 (66.7%)	0	1 (33.3%)
Mother's occupation			
House wife	23 (67.9%)	5 (15.2)	5(15.2%)
Trader	6 (75%)	2 (25%)	0 (0)
Student	2 (100%)	0 (0)	0 (0)
Civil servant	3 (75%)	0 (0)	1 (0)
Self employed	1 (33.3)	0 (0)	2 (66.7%)
Mother's level of education			
Primary	12 (92.3%)	0	1 (7.7%)
Secondary	14 (58.3%)	6 (25%)	4 (16.7)
Tertiary	8 (66.7%)	1(8.3%)	3 (25.0%)
None	12 (92.3%)	0 (0)	1 (7.7%)
Gestation			
Preterm	6 (66.7%)	1 (11.1%)	2 (22.2)
Term	28 (66.7)	6 (14.3%)	8 ((19.0%)

Table 5: Other laboratory parameters/test results. The results, as shown in Table 4, are within normal limits for infants as well as the mothers.

Lab tests/parameters	Infants		Mothers	
	Mean (SD)	Median (IQR)	Mean (SD)	Median (IQR)
Albumin (g/dl)	45.2(8.9)	44(40-49)	43.8(3.2)	43.0(41.3-45.0)
Calcium (mmol/l)	2.3(0.2)	2.3(2.2-2.5)	2.5(0.2)	2.5(2.3-2.6)
Phosphorus (mm/l)	1.1(0.2)	1.1(1.0-1.2)	1.1(0.1)	1.191.0-1.2)
Alkaline Phosphatase (iu/L)	213.7(46)	211(182.5-241.0)	126.5(16.0)	124(114.5-132.0)
Creatinine (μ m/L)	34(8.6)	33(29-38)	59.5(13.4)	58.5(50.3-69.0)
Urea (mmol/l)	3.1(2.0)	2.6 (2.0-3.3)	3.6(1.4)	3.3(2.8-4.0)

Discussion

The pilot study yielded prevalence rates for vitamin D deficiency and insufficiency for both infants and their

mothers. It was also possible to compute the mean and median levels of vitamin D for both infants and their mothers. This is an indication that the research methodology (data collection and analysis), if applied to the proposed multicentre study, can generate data to answer the research questions and achieve the study objectives. Furthermore, the pilot study showed a vitamin D deficiency rate in infants of 18.9%, a figure higher than the 9.3% reported in Jos from a neighbouring state (Plateau) in 2023¹⁰. It is worthy of note, however, that a similar study conducted in Jos about 3 decades earlier had indicated that vitamin D deficiency did not exist among young children in Jos.¹¹ This observational trend may be a pointer to the need for further investigations on the status of vitamin D in infants in Nigeria. The prevalence rate from the pilot study has provided vital information that can be used for the calculation of sample size for the proposed multicentre study.

The results of the pilot study uniquely showed lower maternal mean vitamin D levels as well as higher

maternal vitamin D deficiency rate when viewed alongside those of their infants, suggesting that the infants may be exposed to sources of vitamin D other than breast milk. Breast milk accounts for only 20% of an infant's daily requirement of vitamin D.² The regular use of hijab by the mothers would hinder their ability to synthesize vitamin D from sunlight, as has been noted previously,¹² and this may account for their low vitamin D levels. The data were, however, not subjected to inferential statistics because the sample size of the pilot study was not adequately powered to do so, as this was not the primary aim of the pilot study.

We documented a consent refusal rate of 10%. Eighty per cent of participants who declined said they needed to get their husbands' opinion. The other reason for consent refusal was the involvement of bloodletting, which they claimed was a painful procedure. The study area is a predominantly Muslim community, and the role of the father as the household head in the Islamic culture explains the inability of the women to provide independent consent for research. This underscores the need for consideration of cultural differences at the participating centres while designing the consent form for the main study.

The question on maternal occupation in the protocol would need to be modified to address the extent of exposure to the major source of vitamin D (sunlight), and this would be more forthcoming with a question on the number of hours spent outdoors per day.

The rate of consent refusal (10%) is lower than that reported by SJ Thaker et al¹³ from India (21%), which was a review of several studies, some of which were interventional and required multiple blood collections. We believe the low consent refusal rate in this study may be because the consent information form was read out to participants' mothers and interpreted for those who spoke only the local language. The implication of this for the larger study is that the consent form will be interpreted and translated into the local languages at the participating centres.

The research data collection process was noted to prolong patients' waiting time and was also associated with longer clinic time for the doctors. It might therefore be necessary to consider engaging the services of a doctor solely for data collection and phlebotomy for the research period, and the cost of this factored into the budget. This is likely to reduce the total time required for the conduct of the research. The other modifications to the questionnaire will include details on the length of time mothers spend outside of the home as a measure of exposure to sunlight, since this may be more informative than their occupation.

The pilot study revealed that while the question on the mode of dressing by mothers (use of hijab) was relevant, the follow-up question on the colour of hijabs provided no additional useful information because each mother had different colours of hijab worn at different times. This follow-up question should therefore be expunged from the protocol.

The result showed that infants on mixed feeding (BM+BMS) tended to have higher vitamin D levels than

infants on predominant breastfeeding. Although not statistically analysed, this finding underscores the urgent need for a guideline on routine vitamin D supplementation for infants in Nigeria while discouraging the routine use of breast milk substitutes, which have numerous negative health implications.

Materials for sample collection, as well as reagents for laboratory analyses, amounted to N20,750 per mother-infant pair. This is important information that would be required when preparing the budget for the proposed multicentre study.

Study limitation

Samples were stored for up to two months in order to accrue sufficient numbers for analysis, since once reagents were reconstituted, they had to be used up within 7 days of validity. This extended the completion time of the pilot study. It is hoped that centralised sample collation and analysis during the multicentre study will obviate this problem.

Conclusion.

The results of the pilot study on vitamin D prevalence in infants indicate that the adopted methodology is capable of achieving the objectives of the study (generating the prevalence of vitamin D deficiency in infants as well as assessing the factors that may be associated with vitamin D deficiency). Additionally, the protocol for data collection would require some modifications to capture relevant information more adequately, while recommendations for the recruitment of a dedicated staff for data and sample collection, as well as centralised sample analysis, are made to shorten the research duration. The pilot study also provided information on the cost of laboratory reagents, which is an important component of the budget for the proposed multicentre research.

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Role of authors

LIA: was involved in Conception and design of work, data acquisition, analysis and interpretation, drafting of manuscript, and critically reviewing for intellectual content, approval of final content for publication, and agreed to be accountable for all aspects of the work

MOY: Was involved in the design of work, data acquisition, analysis, and interpretation, critically reviewing the manuscript for intellectual content, approval of final content for publication, and agreed to be accountable for all aspects of the work.

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